

EXPECTED ROLE OF TEACHER IN DEVELOPING AWARENESS TOWARDS ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract:

Environmental problems are wide spread agreement these days among the biggest problems facing human kind. The environmental problem is increasing day by day. This is due to the adaptation of consumers' life style and general apathy what the surrounding. It is the education which can make the human beings conscious and knowledgeable about environment and environmental problems. So, environmental education is needed. Students must have awareness about environment and the problems associated with it so that they can play their role very effectively. The full length paper describe the environmental problems, environmental awareness and role of teacher to impart environmental education, how a well-informed and trained teachers can help students become more aware of the environment with the application of some teaching methods at school.

Key words: Environment, Environmental Problems, Environmental Education, Environment Awareness

Introduction

Education plays a very important role in the life of man. It is this tool that makes a man a human being who can think, analyze and act judiciously. Many philosophers, thinkers and educationists have defined education in many ways from different viewpoints. If we sum up all the definitions, then we can define education as “that process which brings a change in the behavior of human being”. I would further hold that “a change in behavior in a desired manner”.

The rapid changes and increased complexity of today's world present new challenges and put new demands on our education system. There has been generally a growing awareness of the necessity to change and improve the preparation of students for productive functioning in the continually changing and highly demanding environment. In confronting this challenge it is necessary to consider the complexity of the education system itself and the multitude of problems that must be addressed. Clearly, no simple, single uniform approach can be applied with the expectation that significant improvements of the system will occur.

Environmental problems are wide spread agreement these days among the biggest problems facing human kind. We may not face an environmental crisis, for ecological disasters for few days due to the advance developed technologies by the scientists. But we do face a crisis in our conception of ourselves and of our relations to our surroundings. Reflection on these matters is timely for the future of both humanity of the many other species whose survival is in our hands. Whenever society faces large problem, there is a tendency to think that either their roots or their solutions lie at least partly in the educational system. This is as true of environmental troubles as it is of football hooliganism, racism and the child abuse.

Environmental problems are not at all new phenomena. The environmental problem is increasing day by day. This is due to the adaptation of consumers' life style and general apathy what the surrounding. In the present sceneries environmental hazard produce danger for the survival of human race and others. However, after the

Second World War the exponential growth of ecological problems has broadly run parallel with the population explosion in developing countries and the development of technology and affluence in industrialized societies. It is obvious that the equilibrium of the biosphere is changed and that the environment is shaped by man's adaptation to his surroundings and by the social systems he creates as his second nature.

Preservation of environment is fundamental need of humanity which is accepted by everyone in the first international conference on environment in Stockholm in 1972. Climate change, forest destruction, acid rain, desertification and global warming like some imported issues discussed in prithvi shikhar sammelan at Brazil in 1992 in riode Janeiro. After the report of IPCC (2007), international community in Bali conference on climate change (2007 emphasized on the reduction of green house gases particularly CO₂ and CH₄. All participants from about 188 countries arrived at a final draft to follow the Kyoto- Protocol (1997) terms and conditions as soon as possible.

Environmental problems are not all new phenomena. In the present sceneries environmental hazard produce danger for the survival of human race and others. However, after the Second World War the exponential growth of ecological problems has parallel with the population explosion in developing countries and the development of technology and industrialized societies. It is obvious that that the biosphere is changed and the environment is shaped by man's adaptation to his surroundings and the social system he creates as his second 'nature'.

Polluted environment endangers the human race by threatening its survival on planet. Boundaries of any nation cannot limit these environmental problems to a particular country and region, but its impact is global one. This large scale environmental degradation has caused a global concern about the conservation and protection of the earth's environment. Hence effort must be made for inculcating environmental consciousness or awareness among the masses. It is the education which can make the human beings conscious and knowledgeable about environment and environmental problems. Moreover, awareness is essential for the action. The main purpose of environmental education in schools is to acquaint and sensitize the young minds to the environmental and concerns, to inculcate in them healthy personal and social attitude and behavior towards environment.

From the time a child is a pre-scholar, and throughout his school years, the job of exposing children to the world around them is an essential pre-requisite or foundation to learning that is often neglected by parents who are not conscious of this need.

Environmental Awareness

What is environmental awareness? It is having knowledge of the surroundings, or world, beyond ones immediate place. Often educators and parents assume that children notice what they, the parents, see or understand what they know about their surroundings. This, however, is often not the case. Children are not naturally aware of their changing environment and often do not have the background that adults have to understand their environment. Environmental awareness needs to be taught.

Thus, students must have awareness about environment and the problems associated with it so that they can play their role very effectively.

Environment is the utmost important part of our lives. It is concerned with the surroundings in which we live and cherish our life. Protection of environment is everyone's duty. So environment education is needed.

Conservation of environment is not taken seriously by people. There is a “who cares” attitude or “the little I pollute, how does it matter much?” attitude. These attitudes are because of the lack of environment education. Effective learning happens in childhood to make environment education effective. The people who shoulder this responsibility are to be trained, hence the importance of teacher educators.

NEW DELHI SEPT. 6. Stressing the need for taking up environment-related issues more prominently in schools, the former President, K.R. Narayanan, today said teachers could play a pivotal role in nurturing attitude and values among children for developing a better environment and making them realize their duties and role in preserving the earth.

Mr. Narayanan, who was addressing a workshop on "Role of Teachers for Better Environment" in the Capital, said, "Teachers have always played an immensely important role for the progress and development of society. At a time when mankind is threatened by environmental disaster endangering the very existence of life on earth, the role of teachers has become all the more important."

Pointing towards the students' successful campaigns against use of polythene bags and use of firecrackers, the former President said students of the Capital had proved that they could also make a difference in preserving environment. "Growth of such healthy attitude among children augurs well for a sustainable future at the forefront of which remain school teachers and their pupils."

Role of Teacher

In order to protect and conserve the environment, enabling people to lead quality life, emphasis has been given to environmental education in both formal and non formal system of education. Informal system of education, teacher can play an important role in educating their students about environmental awareness. So, environmental education is needed. A properly planned syllabus and activities appropriately calculated and executed will bring the desired change. Protection of environment is everyone's duty.

Teachers themselves need a good training so that they can become effective. The primary teachers are trained at DIET training institutes (both private and government) and the high school teachers are trained at B.Ed institutes (both private and government) and M.Ed at postgraduate level. The people or master trainers are called “The teacher educators”. These teacher educators plan the syllabus and the training schedules for the training of the candidates. They influence these would be teachers who would take the burden and shoulder the responsibility of training (educating) the future generations. Hence, they are of prime concern.

If teacher may to help their students obtain more extensive knowledge and awareness of the environment, then they would be able to create teaching situations in which children's idea and skills can be challenged and /or extended since some different occasions should be created for children to gain knowledge and awareness for the environment. Teachers have to strive to provide their students with many opportunities to expand their knowledge by actively participating in an environment that is appropriate for their level of development. For example environmental campaigns should be organized at schools for students to know about the environment.

The teacher as coach organizes and facilitates a safe and motivating learning environment and promotes learning taking account of personal and cultural differences of learners based on psychological insights. The teacher as developer develops and evaluates learning environments differences in the broadest sense with regard to personal and cultural. The well-informed and trained teachers can help students become more aware of the environment with the application of some teaching methods at school.

Importance of Teacher Education for Environmental Awareness

Effective learning happens in child hood to make environment education effective. The people who shoulder this responsibility are to be trained, hence the importance of teacher educators. If the “would be” teachers are trained in conservation and protection of environment then the cascading effect can be seen in the following way. The impact can be seen at two levels- i.e. at the school level and at the teachers’ training institute level.

Teacher education has been described by UNESCO as ‘...the priority of priorities...’ in environmental education (UNESCO 1990). Despite the emphasis on environmental education, many provincial education departments do not have the expertise or funds to run development programs to support teachers with environmental education.

The National Botanical Institute (NBI) is one of many parastatal and non-governmental organizations with an interest in environmental education to provide resources for teachers and learners. Our Teacher Capacity Building: Skills Development through Environmental Education Workshops is one such initiative. This is a two-year project administered and facilitated by the NBI and funded by the South African National Commission for UNESCO.

Conclusion:

Environment is the utmost important part of our lives. Protection of environment is everyone's duty. So environment education is needed. In order to protect and conserve the environment, enabling people to lead quality life, emphasis has been given to environmental education in both formal and non-formal system of education. Informal system of education, teacher can play an important role in educating their students about environmental awareness. For a well-trained and well informed teacher that imparts environmental education to their students, it is necessary that teacher educated should be given properly. So, we can conclude that teacher and teacher education both play a prominent role in conserving our environment.

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